

STUDY OF EFFICACY OF KRISHNA CHOORNA VATI WITH YOG BASTI IN COMPARISON TO RASNA GUGGUL WITH YOG BASTI IN MANAGEMENT OF VATAKAPHAJ GRIDHRASI

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ABSTRACT

Gridhrasi is one of the Vatavyadhis in which the pain starts from hip and gradually comes down to waist, back, thigh, knee and foot affecting these parts with stiffness, distress and piercing pain. These symptoms are of Vata but when disordered is caused by Vata and Kapha causing drowsiness, heaviness and anorexia.^[1] The signs and symptoms of Gridhrasi resembles to that of Sciatica. There is a need of evaluation of certain ayurvedic clinical therapies on various scientific parameters which could be safe, effective and readily available. So this clinical trial had been selected. Krishna (pippali) choorna is given bhavana of gomutra and erand tel, this formulation is used for treatment of Vatakaphaj Gridhrasi.

KEYWORDS: Gridhrasi, Vatavyadhi, Krishna, pippali, gomutra, erand tel.

INTRODUCTION

Present life style compels man to adopt the speed. Conditions prevailing all over the country like bad roads, polluted atmosphere, altered food habits are great hurdle. This causes stress and strain on the body. To maintain present existing life style, one has to become irregular and natural life cycle is disturbed. In present civilized era, the vehicular travelling is increasing day by day and due to uneven roads, obstacles cause injury to vertebral column. Malnutrition also supports by way of destructing the tissues that results

into compression of sciatic nerve and also provokes Vatadosha. The disease prevails in about 30 % of population.

There is a need of evaluation of certain ayurvedic clinical therapies on various scientific parameters which could be safe, effective and readily available for treatment of Vatakaphaj Gridhrasi Vyadhi. So this clinical trial had been selected.

Krishna (pippali) choorna is given bhavana of gomutra and erand tel, this formulation is used for treatment of Vatakaphaj Gridhrasi.^[2]

AIM

To study effect of Krishna Choornavati with Yog basti in Vatakaphaj Gridhrasi in comparison to Rasna Guggul with Yog basti.

OBJECTIVES

- To study the efficacy of Krishna choornavati with Yog basti in Gridhrasi.
- Comparative study of above effect with Rasnaguggul along with Yog basti in Gridhrasivyadhi.
- To study the role of age, sex, occupation, etc. in relation to Gridhrasi.

DRUG REVIEW

Name	Ras	Virya	Vipak	Guna	Actions
1) Pippali	Katu	Anushna-sheet	Madhur	Laghu Snigdha Tikshna	Kaphavatanashak
2) Erandtel	Madhur Katu Kashaya	Ushna	Madhur	Snigdha Tikshna Sukshma	Virechak Vatakaphashaman
3) Gomutra	Madhur tikta	Ushna	Madhur Tikta Katu	Laghu Dipana	tridoshashamak

MATERIALS AND METHODS

	Group A	Group B
Drug	Krishna choorna vati	Rasna Guggul
Duration of therapy	2 months	2 months
Follow up	8th, 15th, 30th, 45th and 60th day.	8th, 15th, 30th, 45th and 60th day.
Follow up without treatment	Next 4 months	Next 4 months
Detail therapy	Yog basti for initial 8 days	Yog basti for initial 8 days
Dose	500mg BD ^[3]	500 mg BD
Kaala	Vyana Kaala (after meals)	Vyana Kaala (after meals)
Anupana	Luke warm milk ^[4]	Luke warm milk

Criteria for assessment

For subjective parameters following symptoms were assessed

1. Padshoolkramasha (lancinating pain) (nitamba to padanguli).
2. Graha (stiffness)
3. Spandana in region of Gridhrasinadi (nerve pulsation)
4. Gamana and asana kashtata (pain on flexion and extension of hip joint)
5. Aruchi (anorexia, dystaste)
6. Malavarodha (constipation)

Objective criteria

1. SLR test
2. SNDT test
3. Lasegue test

Grade

- Padshool kramasha (nitambatopadanguli) (lancinating pain)
 - Nopain-0
 - Mild pain-1
 - Moderate pain with no difficulty in walking-2
 - Slight difficulty in walking due to pain-3
 - Much difficulty in walking due to pain-4
- Graha (stiffness)
 - Nostiffness-0
 - Mildstiffness-1
 - Moderate stiffness-2
 - Much difficulty due to stiffness-3
- Spandan in region of Gridhrasinasi (nervepulsation)
 - Nopulsation-0
 - Mildpulsation-1
 - Severepulsation-2
- Gamana and asana kashtata (pain on flexion and extension of hip joint)
 - Nopain-0

- Pain without wincingofface–1
- Pain with wincingofface–2
- Patients shouts orprevents flexion–3
- Do not allow passive movement–4

- Aruchi (anorexia, dystaste)

- Noaruchi–0
- Mild (hunger 2 times a day)–1
- Moderate (hunger 1 time a day) –2
- Severe (total losso fhunger)–3

- Malavarodha (constipation)

- Once daily with satisfaction–0
- Oncedailywithoutatisfaction–1
- Twicedailywithoutatisfaction–2
- Alternateday-3

B) Clinical criteria

1. SLR test No pain –0

Pain at 90 degrees – 1

Pain at 60 degrees – 2

Pain at 45 degrees – 3.

2. SNDT

Severe tenderness – 3 Moderate tenderness – 2 Mild tenderness – 1

No tenderness – 0

3. Lasegue test

No pain –0

Pain at 90 degrees – 1

Pain at 60 degrees – 2

Pain at 45 degrees – 3.

OBSERVATION

Degree of SLR Before treatment

	Group A	Group B
25 degree	23	21
25–70 degree	65	63
70–90 degree	02	06
Free (no pain)	00	00
Total	90	90

Degree of SLR After treatment

	Group A	Group B
25 degree	01	15
25–70 degree	37	39
70–90 degree	52	36
Free (no pain)	00	00
Total	90	90

Total effect of the Therapies

Improvement	Group 1	Group2
	0	0
Cured MarkedlyImproved	80	30
Improv	7	25
Benefited Stable Deteriorated	0	14
	3	21
	0	0

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS**Hypothesis**

Null Hypothesis– Krishna choornavati with Yog basti is equally effective as compared to Rasna Guggul with Yog Basti in management of Vatakaphaj Gridhrasi.

Alternatethypothesis– Krishna Choorna with Yog Basti is more effective in comparison to Rasna Guggul with Yog Basti in management of Vatakaphaj Gridhrasi.

Statistical Analysis of Symptoms in Group A (Krishna Choorna with Yog Basti).

Cardinal signs and symptoms	No. of patients	Mean symptom score BTAT	M. D.	$\sum(X-\text{mean})^2$ BTAT	% Relief	S.D. BTAT	SE	Obtain edz	P Value	Significance
Paadshool	90	3.1 1	2.2	38 14	70.22 %	1.31 0.48	0.24 5	8.98	<0. 001	HS
Graha	90	2.4 0.6	1.8	13.5 14.8	69.1 %	0.46 0.51	0.18	9.98	<0. 001	HS
Gamana and	90	3.3	2.2	14.8	74.43	0.52	0.19	11.6	<0.	HS

asana kashtata		0.87		16.9	%	0.54	2	69	001	
Spandana (in sciatic nerve)	90	1.25 0.24	1	1.5 1.12	78.99 %	0.20 0.16	0.22	4.63	<0.001	HS
Aruchi	65	1.31 0.29	0.4	1.43 1.4	82.5 %	0.24 0.24	0.262	5.46	<0.001	HS
Malavarodha	75	2.33 0.48	1.7	12.16 5.5	74.61 %	0.92 0.42	0.31	5.5	<0.01	S
				Total % relief	64%					

Statistical Analysis Of Symptoms In GroupB (Rasna Guggul with Yog Basti)

Cardinal signs and symptoms	No. of patients	Mean symptom score BT AT	M.D.	$\sum(X\text{-mean})^2$ BT AT	% Relief	S.D. BT AT	SE	Obtained z	P value
Paadshool	90	2.4 1.7	0.7	36 26.1	30.78%	1.24 0.91	0.26 27	2.7	<0.02
Graha	90	2.1 1.5	0.6	18.8 17.3	29.92%	0.68 0.6	0.20 37	2.9	<0.01
Gamana and asana kashtata	90	2.6 2	0.6	24.1 18.4	24.8%	4.2 3	0.85 73	0.71	>0.1
Spandana	90	1.6 1.2	0.4	1.2 0.8	26.63%	0.3 0.2	0.31 62	1.2	>0.1
Aruchi	67	1.6 1	0.6	1.36 1.2	38.34%	0.27 0.41	0.3	1.9	<0.05
Malavarodha	70	1.9 1	0.9	4.9 4.1	47.21%	0.7 0.58	0.39 75	2.31	<0.02
				Total % relief	32%				

Statistical Analysis For Comparison between After Treatment Score of both Groups (A and B)

Mann Whitney Utest

Cardinal signs and symptoms	No. of patients AB	Mean symptom score AT AB	M.D.	$\sum(X\text{-mean})^2$ AB	S.D.	SE	Obtained U	P Value	Significance
Paadshool	90 90	1 1.8	0.7	14.3 26.5	0.84	0.213	3.2	< 0.01	V.S.
Graha	90 90	0.81 1.6	0.8	14.3 17.2	0.741	0.2	4.21	<0.001	H.S.
Gamana and asana kashtata	90 90	0.94 2.1	1.03	16.97 18	0.78	0.18	5.168	<0.001	H.S.
Spandana	90 90	0.25 1.2	0.95	1.13 0.84	0.41 0.45	0.235	3.87 75	<0.001	V.S.

Aruchi	65 75	0.3 1	0.7	1.43	0.49 0.633	0.318	2.24	<0.0 5	S
Malava rodha	67 70	0.5 1	0.5	5.5	0.651 0.76	0.32	1.57 3	<0.1	N.S

By referring the table, the value is significant at the level < 0.001 . Hence, null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted. Thus there is significant difference in both treatment and Krishna Choorna with Yogbasti is more effective in treatment of Paadshool symptom in comparison with Rasna Guggul.

DISCUSSION

Krishna choorna with Errand tel and Gomutra is effective in KaphaVatajGridhrasi.

Krishna choorna with its Ushna, Tikshnaguna leads to Shoolanashan and Vyadhiprashaman in gridhrasivyadhi.

Errand taila is Madhur, tiktarasatmak with madhurvipak leading to vatakshaya property. Gomutra is good digestive, laxative and neutralizing agent against toxin and tridoshadushtinashan and decreases Vata disorder.^[5] Basti, described as half treatment by Acharya Charak leads to Vata Shaman and causes relief.^[6] Pippali should not be used in large quantity for long time.^[7] The nervous system is the major controlling, regulatory and communicating system in the body. It is the center of all mental activity including thought, learning and memory. Role of neurotransmitters plays essential role in Vatavyadi. Vata is responsible for all the movements in the body. Diseases caused by Vata in its vitiated condition is called as Vatavyadhi. Vata doesnot produce disease in everyone. Only vitiated Vata is responsible for causing diseases.

CONCLUSION

On the basis of the study of literature and clinical trials of patients, following conclusions have been drawn.

Gridhrasi is a burning problem in present day lifestyle.

Gridhrasi Vata Vyadhi can be very effectively managed with Krishna Choorna and YogBasti. Krishna Choorna with its Madhur Vipaka and Vatashaman property relieves symptoms of Gridhrasi.

Errand tail and Gomutra were found to be specially useful in Gridhrasi due to Margavarodhajanya Vata Prakopa.

The trial with above medicine has no side effects.

Gridhrasi management with Krishna choorna is more significantly effective than with Rasna Guggul as YogBasti was common in both groups.

Gridhrasi is more common in age group of 51 - 65 years.

Occurrence of Gridhrasi is more in females. More prevalence is seen in urban area.

Incidence of Gridhrasi is more in middle economic status.

Gridhrasi is common in patients coming with veg diet and Katu rasa in Ahara. Incidence of Gridhrasi is more in VatakaphajPrakriti.

Incidence of Gridhrasi is more in patients with Madhyam satva.

In the present study both the group showed result but the total percentage of relief was more in trial group than control group.

The current study has opened a new chapter in Gridhrasi which needs a favourable trial in the management of Gridhrasi.

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